

Tensile Properties of Carbon and Glass T-joints as a Structural Element of Wind Turbine Blade

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1 Introduction

Wind turbines are recognized as classic examples of structures where the operating lifetime of the structure is controlled by the fatigue properties of the material [1]. This is exacerbated by the 2D nature of the composite materials used in blade construction which are typically fabrics in a variety of formats (e.g. NCF, uniweave, woven). The formation of internal detailed shapes within the blade, allowing features such as spars, shear webs and other connections, inevitably requires these 2D material forms to be formed into 3D shapes. This introduces positions within the structure where load transfer occurs across regions with no fibre reinforcement. These weak areas would be natural positions for the initiation of fatigue damage that can occur well before fatigue damage would be expected in the basic material subject to simple in-plane loading.

The aim of this study is to modify and improve the blade structure in order to extend the working life of blade and minimize geometry related fatigue problems. To achieve this goal T-sections have been made as representative elements of the blade's Spar. T-sections have been manufactured from carbon or glass fabrics infused with epoxy resin which have been modified using different toughening techniques, such as the introduction of veil layers, tufting and the use of nano and rubber particle additives to the resin. The additional variables in samples include, the number of veil layers, the veil material.

2 Materials and Method

In this study, the T-joint has been used as a representative connection joint used between spar and skin in wind turbine blades. This connection and associated T-joint has been presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: T-joint in real blade (left) and schematic of T-joint (right).

Composite T-joint specimens have manufactured using different materials as matrix and reinforcement fibres. Materials used for each of these parts have been presented in following sections.

Matrix

Two different resin systems have been used in this experiment, an unmodified epoxy resin and two particle modified epoxy resin systems. The unmodified epoxy resin is a system based on Araldite LY 564, and associated hardener used is XB 3486 which is a formulated amine. This epoxy system is low viscosity and high flexibility system[2]–[4]. The first modified epoxy resin used was Albipox 3001 which is a high performance elastomer-modified epoxy resin based on Bisphenol A/F epoxy resin. The elastomer used in this system was a special nitrile rubber chemically inked to epoxy resin. These elastomer regions were formed via phase separation during curing stage of resin. The second system used was Albopox F091, which is again a modified epoxy resin but with a combination of SiO₂ nano particles and elastomer components. When cured a three phase system is formed consist of micron size elastic domains and nano sized hard domains in a continuous resin matrix. Detail of resins and hardeners used were presented in table 1.

Table 1:Used Resins and Hardeners Data

	Viscosity@25°C (mPas)	Density@25°C (g/cm ³)	Flash Point (°C)
Araldite LY 564	1200-1400	1.1-1.2	185
XB 3484	10-20	0.94-0.95	123
Albipox 3001	22000	1.11-1.14	150
Albipox F091	17000	1.15-1.17	150
Albidur XP 1/609	7000	—	>150

Reinforcement

T-joint specimens were manufactured using a Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding method. Dry carbon or glass fabrics were laid up against an aluminum mould with a triangular cross section in order to provide the necessary support for vertical part of sample. Details of fibres used have been presented in table 2.

Table 2: Fibre Reinforcement Data

	Structure	Fibre Type	Fabric Weight(gsm)
FGE104	±45	E-Glass	609±5%
FGE664	UD	E-Glass	594±5%
38399	Plain Weave	Carbon-6K	375±5%

These fibre reinforced composite specimens were categorized into the following three groups: plain woven carbon fabric specimens, ±45° unweven glass fabric specimens and, 3D woven glass fabric T-sections with layer to layer stitched and angle interlocked structures.

Veil

A major drawback in use of fibre reinforced composite materials is their poor interlaminar toughness under Mode-I and Mode-II loading. In practice this results cause the material to suffer in number of cases. Three dimensional sections such as T- or H-sections created from 2D layers inevitably have lines of weakness resulting in stress transfer problems in structures and early failure by delamination is such a case in wind turbine blades. Different interleaf materials have been developed and tested by researchers during recent years, these included non woven veils [5]–[9], thermoplastic films [10]–[13], thermo set films [14]–[17], and same resin interleafs [18][19]. These randomly

oriented non-woven veil fibres improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of material. The migration of these fibres from the interlayer position into the upper and lower fabric plies during the infusion and curing process provides them with the ability to improve composite interlaminar toughness via fibre bridging mechanism. This mechanism, especially in Mode-I is well known and well reported in the literature [20]–[22].

Three different types of non-woven randomly oriented interleaf veils have been used in this study. Veil layers used in T-joints in flange-skin interface and in web between the two vertical parts of web. Table 3 listed veil materials used in this experiment.

Table 3: Veil Materials used in Experiment

Code	Material	Thickness (mm)	Areal Weight (gsm)	Fibre Diameter (µm)
PA	Polyamide	0.194	28	12
PE	Polyester	0.055	12	15
C	Carbon	0.007	10	7

SEM images of three veil materials used in this experiment have been presented in figure2. Random orientation of fibres in the veil materials is clear.

Figure 2: SEM Images of Veil Materials

After laying-down the fabrics, specimens were impregnated with resin using vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM) method and then cured in an oven. A schematic of the VARTM and finished product is presented in figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic of T-joints

Cured composite specimens have been cut into an appropriate sample size and painted on the side for crack propagation monitoring purpose.

Specimen widths for carbon fibre reinforced specimens were 25mm and for glass fibre reinforced specimens they were 50mm.

An Instron 5582 100kN electromechanical machine was used to examine T-joint specimens subjected to a pull-off test. A 40% drop in tensile load or crack length of 25mm on each side of the sample have been set as test failure criteria.

In order to improve interlaminar fracture behavior of specimens, they have been modified using different methods.

Carbon fibre samples modified by use of different interlaminar veils (i.e. carbon, polyester and polyamide) or different epoxy resins are listed in table 1. Glass fibre specimens were modified by addition of polyester or polyamide veils, tufting with Kevlar yarn, or weaving structure as a 3D structure. The effect of these toughening methods on the T-joint structure have been studied.

3 Results and Discussion

Details of manufactured specimens were presented in table 4 and 5.

Table 4: Carbon T-joint specimen specifications

Code	matrix	weave	Fibre Architecture	Toughening
I-0	LY564	Plain	[plain] ₁₀	N/A
I-C-1	LY564	Plain	Web:[plain] ₁₀ Flange:[Plain] ₅ [C] [Plain] ₅	Carbon Veil
I-C-2	LY564	Plain	web:[Plain] ₅ [C] ₂ [Plain] ₅ Flange:[Plain] ₅ [C] ₂ [Plain] ₅	Carbon Veil
I-PE-1	LY564	Plain	Web:[plain] ₁₀ Flange:[Plain] ₅ [PE] [Plain] ₅	Polyester veil
I-PE-2	LY564	Plain	web:[Plain] ₅ [PE] ₂ [Plain] ₅ Flange:[Plain] ₅ [PE] ₂ [Plain] ₅	Polyester veil
I-PA-1	LY564	Plain	Web:[plain] ₁₀ Flange:[Plain] ₅ [PA] [Plain] ₅	Polyamide veil
F091	Albipox F091	Plain	[plain] ₁₀	Nano SiO ₂
3001	Albipox 3001	Plain	[plain] ₁₀	Rubber Domain

Specimens have been subjected to pull-off load and their failure stress and deflection have been measured. The results were compared in order to define effectiveness of different toughening methods. A typical load-extension curve obtained from test is as follow.

Table 5: Glass T-joint Specimen Specifications

Code	matrix	weave	Fibre Architecture	Toughening
Base	LY564	Not woven	Web: [±45] ₁₀ Flange: [±45] ₁₀ [0] ₅	N/A
PA	LY564	Not woven	Web: [±45] ₁₀ Flange: [±45] ₅ [PA][±45] ₅ [0] ₅	Polyamide veil
PE	LY564	Not woven	Web: [±45] ₁₀ Flange: [±45] ₅ [PE][±45] ₅ [0] ₅	Polyester veil
Tufted	LY564	Not woven	Web: [±45] ₁₀ Flange: [±45] ₁₀ [0] ₅	Tufting (Skin-Flange)

Figure 4: Typical Pull-Out test Graph

As seen in figure 4, the pull-off curve has different stages and after the start of the test a few small drops were recorded in load. These drops are related to initiation of cracks around delta fillet of joint. Initiation and propagation continues on until the crack length reaches a critical value. A sudden drop in the load curve marks the propagation of a major crack which ultimately led to failure of structure. After this initial drop, depending on type of specimen, different behaviors were recorded.

In order to compare test results efficiently, load results have been normalised to surface area of the web part of T-joint where load has been applied. Normalisation plane has been highlighted in figure 3.

3-1 Carbon Fibre Reinforced T-joints

In this section the pull-off tests results of carbon fibre composite T-joints are presented.

Figure 5: Studying effect of veils on pull-off of carbon specimens

Figure 5 shows an improvement in pull-off test results due to the addition of a veil interlayer. Specimens containing Polyamide veils showed the highest normalised load to failure, followed by specimens containing polyester veils with specimens with carbon veils exhibiting the poorest properties. The general effect of adding non-woven veil layers to T-joint specimens were to significantly increase the stress to failure of the structure compared to the control sample which did not contain any veil material.

Figure 6: Addition of veils layer to web part of T-joint

The reason for such behavior can be related to fact that, during the resin infusion stage, veils are form a distinct reinforced tough layer between two surfaces and, hence constituted a tough bond line. The toughness in this layer is potentially derived from a variety of deformation mechanisms involving bridging and plastic yield of the thermoplastic fibres [23], which potentially can increase the fracture toughness of material.

However, the differences recorded from the use of different veil materials may also be related to differences between the strength of the bond between the veil materials and resin in each case.

In next part of this study, effect of reinforcing the web interface in addition to reinforcing flange interface, using veil material, were studied (figure 6). Figure 7 shows the normalised load-extension

curves of T-joints containing different number of veil materials.

Figure 7: Effect of addition of veil to T-joint Web

As showed in figure 7, adding interlayer veil between two parts of T-joint web increased load to failure of T-joint specimen comparing to having veil only between flange and skin which the actual failure happens. Detailed inspection of specimen during test revealed that crack propagation first happens in the web part of sample and then it starts in flange and skin interface. However, when horizontal crack propagation starts, vertical crack propagation slows down severely. By addition of veil layer to the web section of the sample, interlaminar fracture toughness of web increases and therefore crack initiation and propagation delayed. As a result failure strength of the specimen increases by addition of second layer of veil. Studies showed that mechanism involved to increase failure strength of specimen were remain same as for one veil layer specimen, and is crack bridging by veil fibres (figure 8).

Figure 8: Bridged veil fibres between two crack surfaces

Figure 9: Effect of Different Resin systems on Pull-Out strength of T-joints

Figure 9 shows pull-off curves for T-specimens infused with different resins. As showed sample infused with modified epoxy resin containing elastomer regions shows the highest pull-out strength comparing to unmodified epoxy resin and resin containing nano particles plus elastomer regions.

In samples containing elastomer regions and samples with nano particles, cavitation of the rubber particles, followed by the formation of the shear-yielded zone around the propagated crack can help to increase the fracture strength of the specimen [24], in addition mechanisms like crack deflection when the crack front encounters the particles or micro cracks around the particles can also play positive role to increasing the overall fracture toughness of the material [25][26].

Figure 10: Normalised load vs. Deflection of all Carbon Fabric Composite T-joints

Comparison of normalised load to failure and failure deflection of all modified T-joint specimens were presented in figure 10. It can be found that specimen

infused with elastomer modified epoxy resin has highest normalised load to failure among carbon T-joints. However, the disadvantage of using such resin system is high viscosity of resin which makes infusion by VARTM nearly impossible. To reduce resin viscosity, the resin and mould should be preheating which for structures in scale of wind turbine blade is very complex and costly process.

3-2 Glass Fibre Reinforced T-joints

Figure 11: Load-Displacement curves of different Glass fibre composites (specimen coding presented in table 5)

Figure 11 shows typical curves for different glass fabric composite T-joints. Comparing graphs of the base sample and PA veil toughened sample shows that there is no significant improvement gained by addition of the polyamide veil layer. This may have two reasons: 1- the bond between the veil fibres and matrix was weak which leads to very low or no crack bridging or 2- the bond was too strong which caused the crack to deflect from the layer containing veil material and across into another layer. In order to confirm the mechanism involved, SEM examination on fracture surface of T-joint specimen was performed .

Figure 12: SEM Images of Fracture Surface of T-joint Containing Polyamide Veil

The study of SEM images in figure 12 confirms the cross ply translation of the crack and the bypassing of the interface adjacent to the veil. As showed in figure 11 (a) no veil fibres were spotted on fracture surfaces however, closer inspection of surface in figure 11 (b) shows veil material in the ply which crack went through it to the next layer down, with a lower fracture toughness.

As showed in figure 11, T-joint specimens containing polyester veils perform quite well in pull-off tests. The initial small drops in load before reaching maximum load value are due to crack initiation and the next drop is caused by initial propagation of crack which is then arrested by bridging of veil fibres. This cycle starts again with an increase in load and the sequence will repeat until the crack length reaches a critical value and cause sample failure.

Figure 13: SEM image of fracture surface of sample containing Polyester veil

Evidence for bridged veil fibres is shown in the SEM image of the fracture surface presented in figure 13. The white arrows indicate the remains of veil fibres or places where the veil fibres have been pulled out.

In tufted specimens, Kevlar yarn has been introduced in through thickness direction of base sample in order to add reinforcement in direction of load under pull-off test. Looking at result of tufted specimen in figure 11, drops in the load level were recorded after the specimen reaches the maximum normalised load value. These drops are related to failure of tuft lines in the specimen. at the first drop, the crack propagates until it reaches first tuft line, where propagation stops and load starts to increase again. Load increase carries on until reaches tensile strength of Kevlar tuft yarn and failure of tuft is then

been marked by drop in load. These sequence carries on for all three tuft lines in specimen. These lines have been mark by three drops of load in sample's curve.

The concept behind the use tufting technique is to introduce a third direction yarn that can carry out of plane load. These z-binders are used to increase post-impact mechanical properties, impact damage resistance, and delamination resistance of composite laminates [27]. The main toughening mechanism is crack bridging by the through-thickness binder yarns/stitches [28]. However, there are disadvantages associated with tufting. One of which is fibre damage caused by needle penetration through fabric layers during the tufting process. This damage includes broken fibre and resin rich areas which can reduce in-plane properties of the composite. Figure 14 shows one of these damaged areas in an SEM image of the fracture surface of specimen. Broken fibres reduces the number of fibres with the ability of carrying load and resin reach area is a weak area and potential location for crack initiation.

Figure 14: SEM image of fracture surface of tufted specimen. Failed tuft line has been highlighted

Figure 15: Normalised failure load and deflection of different glass fabric T-sections.

Conclusion

We found that in carbon specimens, rubber modified epoxy resin has the highest normalised load to failure. However the high viscosity of such modified resins cause manufacturing problems for large scale structures such as wind turbine blades. For this reason veil modified structures were identified as a preferred method.

For glass fibre specimens Polyester interlayer veil showed the best performance. Tufted T-joints have also showed promising results and would be a very good option for manufacturers as applying tuft on preforms would ease the handling of fibres.

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References

- [1] C. Kong, J. Bang, and Y. Sugiyama, 'Structural investigation of composite wind turbine blade considering various load cases and fatigue life', *Energy*, vol. 30, no. 11–12, pp. 2101–2114, Aug. 2005.
- [2] H. Stenzenberger and A. J. Kinloch, 'Structural Adhesives: Developments in Resins and Primers', *Applied Science Pub., London*, p. 77, 1986.

- [3] A. C. Moloney, H. H. Kausch, and H. R. Stieger, 'The fracture of particulate-filled epoxide resins', *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 208–216, 1983.
- [4] J. Spanoudakis and R. J. Young, 'Crack propagation in a glass particle-filled epoxy resin', *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 473–486, 1984.
- [5] M. Kuwata and P. J. Hogg, 'Interlaminar toughness of interleaved CFRP using non-woven veils: Part 1. Mode-I testing', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 1551–1559, Oct. 2011.
- [6] M. Kuwata, S. Matsuda, H. Kishi, A. Murakami, and P. J. Hogg, 'Impact Resistance of Interleaved FRP Using Non-Woven Fabric as Interleaf Materials', *Journal of the Japan Society for Composite Materials*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 55–61, 2007.
- [7] E. Armstrong-Carroll and R. Cochran, 'Improvement of Delamination Resistance with Carbon Nonwoven Mat Interleaves', *ASTM SPECIAL TECHNICAL PUBLICATION*, vol. 1230, pp. 124–131, 1995.
- [8] Y. Aono, S. Murae, and T. Kubo, 'Static Mechanical Properties of GFRP Laminates with Waste GFRP Interleaf', *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 10, pp. 2080–2085, 2011.
- [9] S.-H. Lee, H. Noguchi, Y.-B. Kim, and S.-K. Cheong, 'Effect of interleaved non-woven carbon tissue on interlaminar fracture toughness of laminated composites: Part I–Mode II', *Journal of composite materials*, vol. 36, no. 18, pp. 2153–2168, 2002.
- [10] M. Yasae, I. P. Bond, R. S. Trask, and E. S. Greenhalgh, 'Damage control using discrete thermoplastic film inserts', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 978–989, 2012.
- [11] S. Matsuda, M. Hojo, S. Ochiai, A. Murakami, H. Akimoto, and M. Ando, 'Effect of ionomer thickness on mode I interlaminar fracture toughness for ionomer toughened CFRP', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 30, no. 11, pp. 1311–1319, 1999.
- [12] F. Ozdil and L. A. Carlsson, 'Mode I interlaminar fracture of interleaved graphite/epoxy', *Journal of composite materials*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 432–459, 1992.
- [13] M. Yasae, I. P. Bond, R. S. Trask, and E. S. Greenhalgh, 'Mode I interfacial toughening through discontinuous interleaves for damage suppression and control', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 198–207, 2012.
- [14] O. Ishai, H. Rosenthal, N. Sela, and E. Drukker, 'Effect of selective adhesive interleaving on interlaminar fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy

- composite laminates', *Composites*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 49–54, 1988.
- [15] N. Sela, O. Ishai, and L. Banks-Sills, 'The effect of adhesive thickness on interlaminar fracture toughness of interleaved CFRP specimens', *Composites*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 257–264, 1989.
- [16] S. Rechak and C. T. Sun, 'Optimal use of adhesive layers in reducing impact damage in composite laminates', *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 569–582, 1990.
- [17] E. Altus and O. Ishai, 'The effect of soft interleaved layers on the combined transverse cracking/delamination mechanisms in composite laminates', *Composites science and technology*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 13–27, 1990.
- [18] M. Hojo, S. Matsuda, M. Tanaka, S. Ochiai, and A. Murakami, 'Mode I delamination fatigue properties of interlayer-toughened CF/epoxy laminates', *Composites science and technology*, vol. 66, no. 5, pp. 665–675, 2006.
- [19] R. Fracasso, M. Rink, A. Pavan, and R. Frassine, 'The effects of strain-rate and temperature on the interlaminar fracture toughness of interleaved PEEK/CF composites', *Composites science and technology*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 57–63, 2001.
- [20] X.-Z. Hu and Y.-W. Mai, 'Mode I delamination and fibre bridging in carbon-fibre/epoxy composites with and without PVAL coating', *Composites science and technology*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 147–156, 1993.
- [21] X. N. Huang and D. Hull, 'Effects of fibre bridging on GIC of a unidirectional glass/epoxy composite', *Composites science and technology*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 283–299, 1989.
- [22] M. S. Madhukar and L. T. Drzal, 'Fiber-matrix adhesion and its effect on composite mechanical properties: IV. Mode I and mode II fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy composites', *Journal of composite materials*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 936–968, 1992.
- [23] D. Tzetzis and P. J. Hogg, 'Bondline toughening of vacuum infused composite repairs', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 1239–1251, Sep. 2006.
- [24] H.-J. Sue, 'Study of rubber-modified brittle epoxy systems. Part II: Toughening mechanisms under mode-I fracture', *Polymer Engineering & Science*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 275–288, 1991.
- [25] A. J. Kinloch and C. Taylor, 'The toughening of cyanate-ester polymers. Part I Physical modification using particles, fibres and woven-mats', *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 433–460, 2002.
- [26] B. B. Johnsen, A. J. Kinloch, R. D. Mohammed, A. C. Taylor, and S. Sprenger, 'Toughening mechanisms of nanoparticle-modified epoxy polymers', *Polymer*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 530–541, Jan. 2007.
- [27] S. Rudov-Clark and A. P. Mouritz, 'Tensile fatigue properties of a 3D orthogonal woven composite', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1018–1024, Jun. 2008.
- [28] A. P. Mouritz, C. Bains, and I. Herszberg, 'Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness properties of advanced textile fibreglass composites', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 859–870, 1999.